

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 4

 Acceptance of papers **April, 2026**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital Object Identifier

Visit the website t.me/scopus_IST2100

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of
Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Professor,
Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), (Malaysia)

Asongu SImplice
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD),
USA

Abdikarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Alimardonov Ilkhom Muzrabshokovich
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Razakova Barno Sayfiyevna
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Khasanov Sarvar Ulugbek ugli
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna
Associate Professor (PhD)

CONTENTS

THE IMPACT OF FINANCIAL RISKS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH DRIVERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THEIR MITIGATION	17
Turopova Nigora Xolmurod qizi	
UTILIZATION OF INTERNAL RESERVES FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL TOURISM (CASE STUDY OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN)	20
Naurizbaev Aliakbar Rustamovich	
MATHEMATICAL MODELS AND ALGORITHMS FOR PROCESSING NOISE DATA	23
Jovlieva Dilnoz Mustofa qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS IN BUSINESS ACTIVITIES AND WAYS TO REDUCE THEM.....	28
Abdukhamid Abdumalikovich Bektemirov	
A MULTI-LEVEL SYSTEM OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR REGIONAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE ASSESSMENT: METHODOLOGY AND APPROBATION	34
Keunimzhaev Mukhamedali Kuanyshaevich	
THE IMPACT OF BANKS ON THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF THE ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	39
Usmonov Faridun Firdavsievich, Ishonkulova Feruza Asatovna	
EMPIRICAL EVALUATION OF MACRO- AND MICROECONOMIC FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY	43
Aytmuratova Ulbike Jalgasovna	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY THROUGH OPTIMIZATION OF PRODUCTION RESOURCE POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	47
Sattarov Abdusamat Umirqulovich	
PROMISING DIRECTIONS FOR APPLYING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN	52
Rakhimova Dilfuza Mirzakasimovna	
PRIORITIES FOR REGULATING FINANCIAL RELATIONS IN PROVIDING HOUSING TO THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	58
Khannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATION OF PRODUCTION COST ACCOUNTING IN FULL-SYSTEM FARMS SPECIALIZING IN THE CULTIVATION OF CYPRINID FISH.....	62
Aitimbetov Amirbek Qoishibekovich	
THE TRANSFORMATIONAL ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS BASED ON 2025 NATIONAL STATISTICS.....	68
Isakjanova Sabokhat Muhamedovna	
AN INTEGRATED METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM MODELS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY ERA.....	79
Rasulova Nigora Yusupovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF COMPANIES.....	83
Kamoliddinov Ilhomjon Muhammadjonovich, Nosirov Eldor Nosirjon ugli	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF THE UZBEK ECONOMY.....	88
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF MARKET FACTORS TO ENSURE THE GROWTH OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE ENTERPRISE (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAG EXPRESS BRAND STORES)	92
Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
THE CONCEPT OF REGIONAL IMAGE AND ITS ECONOMIC CONTENT (THE CASE OF THE KHOREZM REGION).....	99
Dilshod Ibragimovich Ibdullayev	

DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	106
Shakhnoza Samandarovna Ziyadillayeva	
ADVANCED APPROACHES TO THE ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF CURRENT FINANCIAL STABILITY IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES USING CFAR (CASH FLOW AT RISK) AND 3 Σ STATISTICAL RISK MODELS	114
Kurbonov Xayrilla	
DEVELOPMENT OF A PROGRAM FOR ANALYZING MEDICAL LABORATORY RESULTS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS.....	118
Gofurjonov Muhammadali, Kamolov Shamsiddin	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN IMPROVING MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES.....	122
Ubaydullayev Mukhammadjon Abdusamad o'g'li	
IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF ORGANIZATIONS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SERVICES SECTOR.....	125
Ibrohim Meliboyev	
ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVICE QUALITY AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY.....	130
Khudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS IMPROVE USAGE PRACTICES	135
A.A. Ismailov	
E-COMMERCE ADOPTION IN TRADITIONAL STORES.....	140
Nuserov Bakhtiyor	
ENHANCING FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY AND OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF JSC "HUDUDGAZTAMINOT": KEY FACTORS AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGIES.....	146
Ergashev Muhibbek Aslamovich	
METHODS FOR IMPROVING AUTOMOTIVE FUEL QUALITY INDICATORS THROUGH THE USE OF ADDITIVES.....	151
Xushnayev Obid, Sheraliyev Ulugbek, Astonov Alisher	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	156
A.A. Ismailov	
THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING A COUNTRY'S INTERNATIONAL IMAGE: THE CASE OF SWITZERLAND.....	161
Idirisbaeva Hurliman Amanbay qizi, Kurolov Maksud Obitovich	
VOLUNTEER TOURISM: CURRENT IMPACTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS	170
Ossama Moustafa Elsetouhy	
COMPUTER GRAPHICS IN MODERN EDUCATION: PRACTICAL CAPABILITIES OF THE FIGMA PLATFORM.....	176
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
DEVELOPING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.....	182
Abdurasulov Sardor Tolqin ugli	
THE IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT	187
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna, Qosimov Jahongir Ruziboyevich	
STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMIZING THE STRUCTURE OF COMMERCIAL BANK ASSETS AND INCREASING EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN	194
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXPORTS OF PRODUCTS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL FIBERS.....	199
Raximov Furqat Jalolovich	
FUNDAMENTALS OF USING MARKETING RESEARCH TO IMPROVE SALES SYSTEM EFFECTIVENESS.....	206
Abduxalilova Laylo Tuxtasinovna	

FASHION MARKETING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR SHAPING CONSUMER-BASED BRAND VALUE.....	213
Navruz-Zoda Bakhtiyor Negmatovich, Aripova Makhliyo Salakhiddinovna	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, IMPROVING INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES, AND ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN THE FINANCE, BANKING, AND TOURISM SECTORS	220
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi, Uroqov Uchqun Yunusovich	
SOCIAL AND SECURITY PROBLEMS OF INNOVATIVE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION.....	223
Q.A. Musakhanov	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND INNOVATION AS FACTORS OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	228
Ibragimova Saodat Abdumuminovna, Sadullayeva Sevara Uchqun qizi	
THE SOCIAL INSURANCE SYSTEM OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	232
Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li	
DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR TRANSITION TO THE INNOVATIVE MARKETING CONCEPT IN ENTERPRISES UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	236
Bobomurodov Qayimjon Homidovich	
FOMO-DRIVEN PURCHASING IN E-COMMERCE FLASH SALES: AN INTEGRATIVE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	241
Muhammadimov Abdukodir Bakhodirjon Ugli, Arciana Damayanti, Javliev Nuriddin Bektemir ugli	
PHYSICO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COARSE FEEDS	250
Yodgorov Jamoliddin Nomozovich, Yadgarov Sirojiddin Nomozovich	
EVOLUTION AND STANDARDIZATION OF SI MEASUREMENT UNITS IN THE INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM	255
Maxmudov Dostonbek Soyibjon o'g'li	
PROCEDURE FOR ACCOUNTING OF ESTIMATED LIABILITIES BY BUDGETARY ORGANIZATIONS	259
Jabbarova Charos Aminovna	
FEATURES OF AUDIT IN DEVELOPING INVESTMENT LENDING PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	263
Jamshid Mirzakhmedov	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES: THE CASE OF SOLAR AND WIND ENERGY	271
Hayitov Jamshid Kholboyevich	
ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION FINANCING: THE CASE OF THE UNITED KINGDOM	275
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	
THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL DESTINATION IMAGE ON TOURIST SATISFACTION AND REVISIT INTENTION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	279
Shaxnoza Almasovna Ashurova	
METHODS OF THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF METAL FORMING PROCESSES.....	279
Rakhimov T.O., Norboyev Abror Baxtiyor o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF DEVELOPING THE GREEN DEPOSIT SYSTEM IN BANKS WITHIN STATE FINANCIAL POLICY.....	287
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o'g'li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO MANAGING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	293
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	
FINANCING SMALL BUSINESSES AND MECHANISMS FOR ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS	299
Xakimov Akbar Anvarovich	
DIRECTIONS FOR THE APPLICATION OF TAX BENEFITS TO SMALL BUSINESSES	304
Ibrohimov Mukhammadjon Abdullajanovich	

DIRECTIONS FOR THE APPLICATION OF TAX BENEFITS TO SMALL BUSINESSES

Ibrohimov Mukhammadjon Abdullajanovich

University of Business and Science

Senior Lecturer, Department of Finance

ibrohimovmuhammadjon7474@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0008-4449-3691

Abstract. This article examines modern mechanisms for applying tax incentives to small business entities in the national economy, their impact on economic development, and the effectiveness of stimulating entrepreneurial activity through such incentives. It also analyzes the practical aspects of increasing employment, attracting investment, reducing production costs, and simplifying tax administration through the use of digital services.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, tax burden, tax incentives, small business, employment, investment, stimulation.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotida kichik biznes subyektlariga soliq imtiyozlarini qo'llashning zamonaviy mexanizmlari, ularning iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'siri hamda imtiyozlar orqali tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rag'batlantirish samaradorligi ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, raqamli xizmatlardan foydalanish orqali bandlikni oshirish, investitsiyalarni jalb etish, ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini kamaytirish va soliq ma'murchiligini soddalashtirishning amaliy jihatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: tadbirkorlik, soliq yuki, soliq imtiyozlari, kichik biznes, bandlik, investitsiyalar, rag'batlantirish.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются современные механизмы применения налоговых льгот для субъектов малого бизнеса в экономике нашей страны, их влияние на экономическое развитие, а также эффективность стимулирования предпринимательской деятельности посредством льгот. Кроме того, проанализированы практические аспекты повышения занятости, привлечения инвестиций, снижения производственных затрат и упрощения налогового администрирования с использованием цифровых сервисов.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, налоговая нагрузка, налоговые льготы, малый бизнес, занятость, инвестиции, стимулирование.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important directions of the deep reforms being implemented in the economy of Uzbekistan is the support of small business and private entrepreneurship, particularly through reducing their tax burden and simplifying tax procedures. The share of small business in GDP, its role in ensuring employment, and its contribution to the economic activity of regions further increase the importance of tax incentives.

The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 identifies the liberalization of tax policy, the creation of a favorable tax environment for entrepreneurship, and the support of small business entities as priority tasks [1].

In addition, a solid legal framework for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship has been consistently established in the country. The application of tax incentives, the preferential lending system, the protection of entrepreneurial rights, including the introduction of the business ombudsman institution, all contribute to the sustainable development of this sector.

This approach requires the further improvement of tax incentive forms and the mechanisms for their practical implementation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scholars have expressed various views on the role of tax incentives in stimulating economic activity. I.

Schumpeter interpreted entrepreneurship as a process of development driven by innovation, noting that tax incentives can accelerate the adoption of new ideas and technologies. R. Hisrich emphasizes that a reduction in the tax burden increases an entrepreneur's capacity to create value.

In much of the economic literature, tax incentives are regarded as a factor that supports the efficient use of business resources, accelerates capital turnover, and facilitates the entry of new entities into the market. These theoretical approaches confirm the strategic importance of tax incentives for the development of small business.

Milton Friedman argued that reducing the tax burden creates broader opportunities for private initiative and encourages business activity. According to his views, lower taxes allow entrepreneurs to retain more resources for investment and expansion.

Joseph Stiglitz emphasized that well-designed tax incentives can support small businesses, stimulate innovation, and strengthen employment. He noted that tax policy should not only generate budget revenues but also create favorable conditions for sustainable economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methods were used in the study: analytical approach — the content, types, and legal basis of tax incentives were examined; comparative analysis — the experience of Uzbekistan was compared with international practice; empirical analysis — the real tax burden and financial results of small businesses were assessed; and economic modeling — the impact of tax incentives on employment and investment was evaluated.

The methodological basis of the study is aimed at increasing the economic potential of business entities, analyzing the impact of state support measures, and assessing investment processes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Application of tax incentives and their economic impact. The tax system of Uzbekistan has introduced a number of incentives for small businesses. These include a single tax payment system for entrepreneurs whose annual turnover does not exceed a certain threshold, temporary tax exemptions for some newly established enterprises, a reduced social tax rate, additional incentives for export-oriented small businesses, and tax and customs benefits for technopark residents [4].

The economic impact of these incentives is reflected in the following areas:

operating costs are reduced, which increases profit margins;

the number of employees rises, as a lower tax burden allows businesses to expand their payroll;

accumulated financial resources can be directed toward investment activities;

the establishment of new enterprises is accelerated;

creditworthiness improves, since a reduced tax burden creates a more stable income base (Table 1).

Table 1

Types of tax incentives for small businesses and their economic impact [8].

Type of tax benefit	Content	Economic impact on small business
Single tax payment	A single tax payment will be introduced for small businesses instead of several taxes.	he tax burden will be reduced, calculations will be simplified, and the costs of doing business will be reduced.
Temporary tax holidays	Newly established enterprises will be exempted from certain taxes for a period of time.	It will be easier to raise initial capital, the number of new enterprises will increase, and it will have a positive impact on the investment climate.
Reduction of the social tax rate	The amount of social tax paid by employers for small businesses will be reduced.	Hiring will be encouraged, employment will increase, and the wage fund will expand.
Benefits for export-oriented enterprises	Additional tax breaks will be provided for small businesses exporting goods.	Export volumes will increase, foreign exchange earnings will increase, and competitiveness will increase.
Benefits for residents of technoparks and FEZs	Innovative and technological enterprises will receive tax and customs benefits.	New technologies will be introduced, innovative production will expand, startups will develop rapidly.

Digital tax administration (e-reporting, e-license)	Tax reporting and registration processes are carried out online.	Administrative burden is reduced, time is saved, business processes are accelerated and transparency is increased.
---	--	--

Source: prepared by the author based on the analysis.

The table above systematically presents the main types of tax incentives applied to small businesses and their economic outcomes.

Firstly, the single tax payment system is one of the most important incentives for small businesses. It combines several taxes into a single payment, simplifies accounting procedures, and significantly reduces operating costs. As a result, the financial stability of small businesses improves.

Secondly, temporary tax exemptions reduce the financial pressure faced by enterprises during their initial stage of operation. This allows businesses to concentrate the resources needed to establish production processes, leading to faster business formation and growth [6].

Thirdly, reducing social tax rates directly contributes to higher employment. Since employers' expenses decrease, they are able to hire more workers, which supports labor market activity.

Fourthly, tax incentives provided to export-oriented entrepreneurs encourage entry into international markets. This increases the share of small businesses in foreign trade and strengthens economic stability through higher foreign exchange earnings.

Fifthly, tax incentives in technoparks and free economic zones are strategically important for innovative enterprises. Small businesses operating in such areas gain an important platform for the rapid introduction of advanced technologies into production, the commercialization of scientific research, and the development of startups.

Sixthly, digital tax administration is among the most effective measures for small businesses. Online submission of tax reports, as well as the electronic issuance of licenses and permits, saves entrepreneurs time, reduces administrative pressure, and increases the transparency of business processes.

In general, different forms of tax incentives reduce the financial burden on small businesses, expand investment activity, increase production efficiency, and support employment growth. Their complementary nature contributes to the stable and balanced development of the national economy [5].

Regional indicators also show that the impact of tax payments differs across regions, since income sources vary by area and sector.

The share of small businesses in GDP supported by tax incentives in 2024 differs by sector. In agriculture, incentives have covered almost all small entities, while in the service sector tax preferences have expanded to new service segments. In industrial sectors, incentives in technoparks and free economic zones are stimulating production activity [8].

The interrelated effects of tax incentives include the following:

- increasing eligibility for preferential loans;
- creating a favorable financial environment for startups developing in business incubators and accelerators;
- simplifying tax administration through digital services;
- expanding the participation of small businesses in development projects.

However, several issues remain. Some entrepreneurs are not sufficiently aware of the procedures for using tax incentives, certain bureaucratic restrictions in tax administration still exist, and the system for evaluating the effectiveness of incentives has not yet been fully developed.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis shows that the application of tax incentives for small businesses is one of the important factors contributing to economic growth. Tax incentives:

- significantly stimulate entrepreneurial activity;
- create new jobs;
- increase the inflow of investment;
- strengthen the competitiveness of small businesses.

Taking these findings into account, the following recommendations can be proposed:

- prepare practical guidelines for entrepreneurs on the procedures for using tax incentives;
- introduce a "Tax Barometer" system to analyze the tax burden of small businesses;
- establish "Tax Incentive Advisory Centers" under local khokimiyats;
- further expand and simplify digital tax services;
- introduce tax holidays for innovative startups.

The application of tax incentives for small businesses is an important factor in increasing economic activity, expanding employment, encouraging new projects, and strengthening the competitiveness of the national economy. This approach can play a significant role in shaping the country's long-term economic development prospects.

REFERENCES

1. Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”. Tashkent: Uzbekistan Publishing House, 2022.
2. Olim Sabirovich Kazakov. Introduction to Management. Tashkent: Fan Ziyosi Publishing House, 2021.
3. Michael Mescon, Michael Albert, Franklin Khedouri. Fundamentals of Management. Moscow: Delo, 1992. – P. 489.
4. K.I. Muhammadjanovich. “Effective Directions of Development of Entrepreneurship”. Conference Zone, 2022. – P. 129–133.
5. M.Ya. Pogorelova. Economic Analysis: Theory and Practice. Moscow: RIOR, INFRA-M, 2016. – 290 p.
6. L.I. Abalkin, O.I. Volkov, V.Ya. Pozdnyakov. Ekonomika predpriyatiya (firmy): Praktikum. Moscow: INFRA-M, 2016.
7. A.T. Kenzhabayev. Problems of Forming a National System of Informatization of Entrepreneurial Activity. Doctoral Dissertation Abstract. Tashkent, 2005. – 39 p.
8. Small Business in Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2020. – 190 p.
8. Statistika agentligi website information.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 4

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles
Published every
monthly

Directions
Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

 Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

 Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

 Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>